

Predictive maintenance of critical HVAC components to reduce biological risk in public buildings

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Abstract.

The purpose of this document is to provide the employer with guidelines for preventive maintenance, specifically practical recommendations necessary to ensure that the air treatment system does not transmit pathogens to those exposed within office environments for 7-8 hours daily.

Workers may experience symptoms related to their exposure to poorly sanitized HVAC terminals, such as rhinitis, dermatitis, asthma, etc. Therefore, it is crucial to provide the employer with clear guidance on the sanitization or cleaning of air treatment systems.

In this discussion, we will focus on maintenance in terms of biological risk, addressing only the components that meet water and humidity.

Keywords

IAQ, maintenance, antibacterial, sanitization methods, HVAC maintenance

Definitions

Cleaning: A set of activities aimed at removing dust and dirt from surfaces, objects, confined environments, and surrounding areas.

Disinfection: A set of operations designed to sanitize confined environments and surrounding areas by eliminating and inactivating pathogenic microorganisms.

Sanitization: A combination of procedures intended to make an environment healthy through cleaning followed by disinfection.

CFU (Colony Forming Units): A measurement used in microbiology to quantify the number of bacteria or microorganisms present in a sample.

CFU/l: A measurement that indicates the concentration of microorganisms, such as bacteria, in a liter of liquid.

CFU/g: This measurement indicates the concentration of microorganisms, such as bacteria, in a gram of a solid sample, such as food or soil.

Introduction

The extensive production of technical standards and guidelines often lacks operational procedures, which can be found in the best practices of companies specialized in sanitization or in the manufacturer's operational instructions for cleaning and sanitizing products.

After conducting on-site investigations and laboratory tests, the biological risk in confined environments is assessed, and countermeasures are identified as needed. Following the biological risk assessment, the confined environment and consequently the HVAC system can be classified according to the severity of the risk, which, according to NADCA procedures, defines the indoor air quality in one of three categories:

- **Normal Ecology**
- **Rooted Spores and Development Traces:** Indoor environment primarily contaminated by fungi, with rooted and dispersed spores showing traces of actual development, reflecting an unacceptable biological risk.
- **Active Development:** A contaminated environment with visible mold, yeast, or associated spores, indicating a serious risk.

If the risk is deemed unacceptable, it is necessary to intervene, starting with the building's HVAC system, as it is often the site where pathogens proliferate and are dispersed into the environment through mechanical ventilation.

The main action to be taken is the creation of a maintenance plan where the maintenance technician, after evaluating the hygienic conditions of the system, specifies the required maintenance interventions, cleaning or sanitization activities, checks, inspections, and verifications to be carried out immediately or as part of the next scheduled maintenance.

Sanitization should be performed twice a year, before the summer season and before the winter season.

Limits of Contamination in HVAC Systems

Below are the Italian regulatory limits regarding the components of air conditioning systems:

- Water in adiabatic humidification chambers: 10^6 CFU/l
- Water in evaporative cooling towers: 10^6 CFU/l
- Dust: 30,000 CFU/g
- Fungal load on surfaces: 15,000 CFU/g

Disinfection and Sanitization Treatment

Before disinfection, it is necessary to perform thorough cleaning or sanitization of the part to be disinfected. A disinfection treatment involves the destruction of microorganisms after the removal of dirt, dust, and crusts, the aspiration of any liquid residues, washing, surface restoration treatments (e.g., applying anti-rust), and only then proceeding with the aerosol application of specific chemical disinfectants such as:

- Hydrogen peroxide
- Peracetic acid
- Benzalkonium chloride.

A sanitization treatment includes both disinfection and cleaning.

HVAC Components Subject to Bacterial Contamination

This discussion focuses on the critical components where pathogens proliferate in the presence of water and humidity, which must undergo remediation and/or sanitization. These components include:

1. The condensate recovery tray in the humidification chamber, as biofilm or traces of it may be present.
2. Humidifiers.
3. The drain siphon, which must be cleaned and sanitized.
4. The walls of the humidification chamber.
5. Heat exchange coils, which can be subject to microbiological contamination.
6. Cooling towers, which must be emptied and sanitized.
7. The walls of the humidification chamber.
8. System terminals where the condensate collection tray is present.
9. Air ducts, which may show visible traces of microbial growth (mold).

Tank - Humidifiers - Siphon – Walls

The water circulating in the adiabatic humidification section, including the tank, humidifying nozzles, and siphon, must be monitored to evaluate microbial contamination.

The aforementioned components are characterized by the presence of stagnant water, which is a breeding ground for bacteria. If the bacterial load exceeds 10^6 CFU/L, it is necessary to carry out sanitization and follow up with control measures after 15 days to assess the effectiveness of the treatment. In cases where the bacterial load is between 10^3 and 10^6 CFU/L, the cooling tower must be emptied, and the water replaced.

Humidification

Sections

Adiabatic humidification systems with water recirculation (partially replaced and partially recycled) may require more frequent checks due to their potential for bacterial proliferation. For adiabatic humidification sections with recirculation, a frequency of at least biannual checks is recommended, while those without recirculation should be checked at least annually. Checks on steam humidification sections may not be necessary since the steam temperature used in the humidification process ensures

the elimination of potentially present microorganisms.

Heat Exchange Batteries. It is essential to monitor the microbial contamination of the fins. In this case, they should be cleaned and/or sanitized, and a new technical visit must be scheduled.

Cooling Towers. Microbiological monitoring of the water in the cooling tower basin is necessary to assess the extent of microbial contamination (see Attachment 4b). Drainage and cleaning operations should be carried out at least twice a year and always after a period of non-use. During these operations, microbiological checks are usually not necessary. The water in the cooling tower should be replaced at least twice a year, at the beginning and the end of the cold season.

Thermal System Terminals. If the terminal is equipped with a condensate collection tank, it should be emptied and sanitized. Appropriate detergents or dry steam at 180°C can be used for this purpose. This procedure should be performed twice a year.

Air Ducts. Given that a technical inspection has been carried out and mechanical removal of dust and dirt has been performed, including the use of chemical products, it is possible to proceed with sanitization using appropriate nebulizers or atomizers. Advanced technologies offer sanitization solutions such as UV lamps. In some systems, ultraviolet (UV) lamps are installed within the ventilation system to continuously sterilize the air and prevent the proliferation of bacteria and mold. Below, a comprehensive method for the remediation of air ducts will be presented.

A brief explanation of traditional procedures of duct cleaning

The Air Duct Cleaning industry has increasing over the years and offers several cleaning services. A first attempt to classify the air duct cleaning is provided by the European technical norm 12097:1999. The cleanliness of a surface is obviously related to a removing of contaminants in the system in fact guidelines (NADCA, ACE 2006) and national laws recommend the removal source as an appropriate cleaning job.

Traditionally the most popular method is a hand\mechanical (fig.2) removal, either by agitation devices (brushing) (fig.5), or by contact vacuum (fig.3) or by the air sweep method (fig.4) which uses an air blade to dislodge contaminants adhered on the duct walls. The last method is the most common and the most effective in improving IAQ, (fig.13).

In the first case the principle is a contact between the devices and any part of the ductboard, the limitation of the method depend on the shape, the size of the duct and, if exist, the interior fibreglass lined ducting. Another big limitations are when we have corrugated tubes (see fig.1) which connect the main duct with the air diffusers and when a part or the entire net is not accessible.

Fig. 1 Terminal corrugated tube

Some of these disadvantage are overlook by the air system where an high volume of air, outgoing from a nozzle (fig. 7) which, address the particulate (dust, dirt etc.) and microbial contaminants towards a lowest-pressure point.

The tools used are: compressors, vacuum pumps, pneumatic brushes, nozzles, air filtration devices. After dislodging the contaminants and after the vacuum device has captured any kind of contaminants, ductwork is considered cleaned, then the next step consist of spraying chemical products inside ducts by an Ultra Low Volume (ULV) device. Usually, the product inflating is either a biocide or a sanificant or a disinfectant. The decision to use a product or another it follows after a visual inspection or a surface-test aimed to found out a microbial presence. Briefly these are the steps to clean and sanitize a ductwork.

Fig. 2 Mechanical brush method

Source: "Cleaning Fibrous Glass Insulated Ducts," North American Insulation Manufacturers Association,

Fig. 3 Contact vacuum method

(Source: "Cleaning Fibrous Glass Insulated Ducts," North American Insulation Manufacturers Association)

Fig. 4 Air sweep method

Source: "Cleaning Fibrous Glass Insulated Ducts," North American Insulation Manufacturers Association,

Fig. 5 Whirling brushes

Fig. 6 Whirling brush automated

Fig. 7 Collom nozzles provide agitation to dislodging of debris

Source: "Collom enterprises),

The new approach of cleanliness and a case of study.

The method recently developed creates a new interface between the duct and the airflow. If we consider for a moment the grade of cleanliness after the treatment we notice that the grade of cleanliness is comparable with the most popular methods and surely has less dust on the walls. Just talking about the performances of the procedures, business have patented this system with several

variation on it. Anyone use a specific terminology, some use a handmade procedure and other totally computerized, another way to classify the procedures is if the atomizer is fixed (fig.9) or mobile.

Using the terminology of firms, we deal with the encapsulating method which is developed to provide the safety and the regenerating method designed to realize only a new interface where the safety, nowadays is granted as second goal.

We take it for granted that the method should be adequately applied after a visual inspection\video survey but first of all, we have to say that it hasn't all the limitation listed above for the most popular cleaning methods.

The peculiarity of the method is a controlled, and uniform deposition of a tested resin into the duct by qualified workers without any dislodging process. Some firms has developed the system avoiding any human intervention, calculating the deposition of polymeric atomization (fig10) carefully created by air or inert gas, other use an airless spray system with high pressure (200 bars) to atomize the resin. Several parameters of the phenomenon and the quality of the chemical contribute to realize an interface thickness fixed avoiding dripping. For example the interface thick is around 200 μm while cars coating is 40-50 μm . Some method use a negative pressure in the ductwork which help air turbulence and avoiding external spreading of contaminants.

Depending on the encapsulating method or renovation method, both equipment tools and the deposition process is different. If we need safety after microbial contaminant and dirt we have to use an encapsulant and the atomizer is movable on a guide-rail and controlled by a video-camera. The other one use a process of deposition by fixed atomizer which in certain cases could be more then one and placed side by side (fig.11), so that they can realize a new interface of the fluid. The deposition of the latter method need a depressed net and isolated by inflated balls (fig8) or others devices.

Fig. 8 Inflating balls

Source: RE.NOVA srl Italy

In 1990 **INAIL** had to deal with the HVAC system of a skyscraper with annexed premises, the HVAC consist of 13 handling air handling unit, the supply systems and almost 6,000 m of ductworks. The work aimed to improve IAQ because of a neglected maintenance for almost 40 years. The first difficult was to know the real dimension of the ductworks, their spatial layout and the state of use. After a visual survey and drew the whole layout the designer decided to apply the encapsulated method where dirt is glued to the interior walls duct. According to INAIL policy, with this procedure is granted an IAQ safer and a sanitization of air conditioning ducts with a long lasting efficacy.

Operatively, steps are listed here. First of all the ducts had to be accessible then it planned a

hierarchical way to label any duct. The difficult was to identify all the branches of the net and plan a daily encapsulating program without forgetting any duct. In case operators forgot the treatment in a single duct, contaminations would be spread into the inner atmosphere.

Fig. 9 A single atomizer applied in a duct. A pipe is for resin another one is for gas

Source: RE.NOVA srl Italy

Fig. 10 The atomization process

Source: RE.NOVA srl Italy

Fig. 11 Two atomizer in progress

Source: RE.NOVA srl Italy

Fig. 12 Scheme of cleaning by regeneration ductworks

Source: RE.NOVA srl Italy

The product as the core of the procedure.

One of the basic reasons which lead the designer towards this method was the quality of the product. It's a resin, good for masonry, plastic and ferrous materials. It's a styrol-acrylic based in water dispersion, with high and adhesive capacity, chemically resistant, inert even to microorganisms' metabolism.

Formulated with inorganic pigments, free of lead, chromium and heavy metals, and with silicates with lamelliforme structure assuring the waterproofing power of coating. The main characteristic are:

-encapsulates and fixes to the walls all dusting material present in the ducts by means of a quick drying process and so avoiding any cleaning operation and excluding the risk of the dispersion in the

environment of polluting materials;

-it dries quickly and forms an homogeneous white wall having a light flexibility which allows the absorption of eventual dynamic stress and vibrations. Furthermore its scarce permeability to the steam protects the metallic walls of the ducts from oxidation phenomena;

-the air flow in the treated ducts improves by 10%.

Advantages and disadvantages of the methods

Even though several methods of duct cleaning are available, their effectiveness in reducing the level of airborne particulates in residential HVAC systems is unknown because there is a lack of established data and investigation. First of all we have to say that the maximum of contamination tolerable is 1g/m^2 and when the walls of the duct are thoroughly hidden, by rule of thumb we can say that the amount of dirt is more or equal than 20g/m^2 and dust are stratified.

Talking about the most popular methods, cleaning ductworks by Mechanical Brush Method and Contact Vacuum Method there is an electrostatic effect on the walls than, we are not sure to reach the value of 1g/m^2 .

It is right telling that in 1994 the Building Construction Industry Advisory Committee (BCIAC - US) evaluated which duct cleaning traditional methods were effective against fibreglass and to what degree they were effective in improving indoor air quality.

The research identified eight identical homes were each couple of homes were chosen for a cleaning procedure and two homes were used as study controls. Data and samples were collected both before during and after cleaning. Results are shown by the chart below.

NIOSH 7400 (fiber/cc) – Total

Notes: Post readings were taken 48 hours after pre and during.

Fig. 13 Comparison between the three methods in terms of fiberglass in 1cm^3

We think that the most important advantage of the newest procedure, is to cover the surface, by a uniform film for more than 98% without residual dust because there are not agitation then, it has not limitations listed in the second paragraph. The lining is elastic and hard with the well-known quality

Fig. 15 Examples of damaged fiberglass ductboard after the treatment

Fig. 16 Example of rectangular duct pre and post encapsulating treatment

How the method is related to the safety and health of workers

In rifer to the health of the workers in the office buildings, this chemical guarantees the resistance against the proliferation of the most known and dangerous bacteria and fungi for many years (tests on ducts treated with this chemical after 9 years have confirmed the efficacy required) then it guarantees the non-toxicity for the operators and the users.

The encapsulating product, after testing has obtained a recognition from a branch office of a Ministry of health, as a chemical which doesn't interact whit human body and has no free radicals. It is added in formula a biocide which is a non volatile organic molecule free from bactericides having toxic inorganic salt. In the end, the product has an inhibiting activity and resistance against bacterial and fungine attack. A third part laboratory has certified that the efficacy of the product against the bacteria and fungi shown in fig.17 not only by suffocation due the coating action but for chemical action.

Fig. 17 Bacteria and fungi on which the encapsulant product acts.

Norms

UNI EN 15780:2011 “Ventilation for buildings – Ducts – Cleanliness of ventilation systems”

UNI 8065:2019 “Water treatment in heating and cooling systems, domestic hot water production systems, and solar thermal systems”

UNI EN 13779:2008 “Ventilation for non-residential buildings – Performance requirements for ventilation and air-conditioning systems”

UNI EN 15251:2008 “Criteria for the design of indoor environment and the assessment of energy performance of buildings, related to indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting, and acoustics”

UNI 10339 "Ventilation systems for air-conditioning in buildings - Design, installation, commissioning, and maintenance"